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D2.2: Report on Submitted scientific paper on the legal analysis of challenges in relation to fundamental rights, data protection, data sharing, and organization of data repositories including potential technological state of art solutions to increase legal compliance

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ABSTRACT:	Open science entails open and collaborative sharing of data and research results, though “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. When the research data includes data about humans, the free movement of personal data sought through open science must be balanced with the protection of fundamental rights and freedoms of individuals, and in particular their right to protection of personal data. Large-scale processing of special categories of personal data is held to particularly high compliance standards, and non-compliance is heavily sanctioned. The main focus of this report is therefore on processing of special categories of personal data for scientific research purposes, and in

	<p>particular for open science purposes to help ascertain when data can be open, and when it must be closed. Legal challenges pertaining to the use of research data repositories are highlighted. Finally, solutions that may help achieve the open science aim are presented.</p>
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As open as possible, as closed as necessary

Heidi Beate Bentzen

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Abstract

Open science entails open and collaborative sharing of data and research results, though “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. When the research data includes data about humans, the free movement of personal data sought through open science must be balanced with the protection of the fundamental rights and freedoms of individuals, and in particular their right to protection of personal data. Large-scale processing of special categories of personal data is held to particularly high compliance standards, and non-compliance is heavily sanctioned. The main focus of this book chapter is therefore on processing of special categories of personal data for scientific research purposes, and in particular for open science purposes to help ascertain when data can be open, and when it must be closed. Legal challenges pertaining to the use of research data repositories are highlighted. Finally, solutions that may help achieve the open science aim are presented.

1. Introduction

Open science entails open and collaborative sharing of data and research results.¹ Open science may enable reproduction of scientific findings and facilitate new discoveries.² This may increase the efficiency, quality, impact, and responsiveness of science while decreasing resource use. As such, open science is a policy priority for the European Union (EU), evident through the European Commission Recommendation (EU) 2018/790 of 25 April 2018 on access to and preservation of scientific information; Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information; and Directive (EU) 2019/790 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market, which applies to publicly funded research data. On an overarching level, Article 179 of the Treaty on the functioning of the European Union solidifies that one of the main objectives of the EU is to strengthen its scientific and technological bases. A European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is being set up, and the research and innovation program Horizon 2020 included an open access policy that provided open access to publications by default, while the current Horizon Europe program also mandates open access to research data by default, though with the caveat “as open as

¹ European Commission. Open Science. 13 December 2019. Available at https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2019-12/ec_rtd_factsheet-open-science_2019.pdf

[accessed 11 June 2023]

² Mascialzoni D, Bentzen HB, Ljøsne IB, et al. Are requirements to deposit data in research repositories compatible with the European Union’s general data protection regulation? *Ann Int Med.* 2019;170(5):332–334.

possible, as closed as necessary”.³ Open data can be openly accessed. This differs from FAIR data, a set of principles to ensure Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable data.⁴ Not all data can be open, but it can still be FAIR.

The open science policy focus of the EU is mirrored by other research funding agencies and scientific journals. The International Committee of Medical Journal Editors only requires a data sharing statement.⁵ However, some journals require data to be readily available for other researchers to be accepted.⁶ For instance, the Public Library of Science (PLOS) family of journals requires authors to make all data necessary for replicating the scientific findings publicly available without restrictions at the time of publication, unless ethically restricted or legally prohibited.⁷

In fields such as engineering and chemistry, legal questions related to commercialization, intellectual property, and trade secret protection may arise. When

³ European Commission. Open Science. 13 December 2019. Available at https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2019-12/ec_rtd_factsheet-open-science_2019.pdf [accessed 11 June 2023]

⁴ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

⁵ Taichman DB, Sahni P, Pinborg A, *et al.* Data sharing statements for clinical trials: a requirement of the international committee of medical journal editors. *Ann Intern Med.* 2017; 167(1):63–65.

⁶ Ursin G, Bentzen HB. Open science and sharing personal data widely - legally impossible for Europeans? *Acta Oncol.* 2021 Dec;60(12):1555-1556. doi: 10.1080/0284186X.2021.1995894.

⁷ PLOS ONE. Data Availability. Available at <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/s/data-availability> [accessed 11 June 2023]

the research data includes data about humans, as is often the case for instance in medical science, the free movement of personal data sought through open science must be balanced with the protection of the fundamental rights and freedoms of individuals, and in particular their right to the protection of personal data. This is why data should not only be as open as possible, but also as closed as necessary. As such, data sharing about humans for open science purposes, raises particularly complex legal issues, and is therefore the focus of this book chapter.

Article 8 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union provides that everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning them, and furthermore that such data “must be processed fairly for specified purposes and on the basis of the consent of the person concerned or some other legitimate basis laid down by law”.⁸ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation. Hereafter, GDPR) aims to balance free movement and protection of personal data, as seen in its objectives laid out in Article 1.⁹ This balancing is evident through a number of derogations from the main rules of the GDPR, which can be used if the personal data processing is for scientific research purposes. These include exceptions from several data subject rights, and even from some of the fundamental

⁸ Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union. *OJ C 326*, 26.10.2012, p. 391–407.

⁹ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32016Ro679&from=EN>.

data protection principles. It is, for instance, allowed to process personal data for scientific research purposes even if the data originally was processed for another purpose. In other instances, this would have constituted a breach of the principle of purpose limitation, but if the further processing is for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, and the conditions of Article 89(1) of the GDPR are met, such further processing shall not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes.

However, the GDPR does not define “scientific research”, making it challenging to know which activities are afforded the possibility to adhere to the more lenient rules. Elsewhere, I have reviewed the jurisprudence related to scientific research from the Court of Justice of the European Union and the European Court of Human Rights. I found that the courts tend to rely on three assessment criteria when deciding whether something constitutes scientific research: 1) the role of the legal entity; 2) the role of the person(s) carrying out the activity; 3) quality standards, including scientific methodology and scientific publication.¹⁰ Furthermore, I suggested adding a fourth criterion, 4) an ethical assessment, including respect for context.¹¹ The United Nations Special Rapporteur on the Right to Privacy subsequently included these four criteria as part of the definition of scientific research in the global Recommendation on the protection and

¹⁰ Bentzen HB. In the name of scientific advancement: How to assess what constitutes ‘Scientific research’ in the GDPR to protect data subjects and democracy. In: Terzis G, Kloza D, Kuzelewska E, Trottier D (eds.) *Disinformation and Digital Media as a Challenge for Democracy*. Intersentia (2020), 341-366.

¹¹ Ibid.

use of health-related data.¹² The manner in which the term is understood by the courts do not currently support the inclusion of activities such as citizen science and open education as “scientific research”, however, these may be emerging categories that may be included in the term in the future.

Compliance with the GDPR is mainly important to ensure protection against the loss of privacy, and protect against harm and discrimination of the individuals to whom the data relates, but compliance is also crucial to avoid incurring sanctions. Infringements are subject to administrative fines up to EUR 20 million, or in the case of an undertaking, up to 4 % of the total worldwide annual turnover of the preceding financial year, whichever is higher. Recently, Meta Platforms Ireland Limited (formerly Facebook) was fined EUR 1.2 billion by the Irish Data Protection Authority.¹³ Scientific research may entail large-scale processing of special categories of personal data, defined in Article 9 of the GDPR as “personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation”. Processing of such data is as a main rule prohibited, and only allowed if specific conditions laid out in Article 9 of the GDPR are met. Understanding which personal data is processed, by

¹² United Nations Special Rapporteur on the Right to Privacy. Recommendation on the protection and use of health-related data. Available at https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/Documents/Issues/Privacy/SR_Privacy/UNSRP_healthrelateddataRecCLEAN.pdf [accessed 11 June 2023]

¹³ European Data Protection Board. 1.2 billion euro fine for Facebook as a result of EDPB binding decision. 22 May 2023. Available at https://edpb.europa.eu/news/news/2023/12-billion-euro-fine-facebook-result-edpb-binding-decision_en [accessed 11 June 2023]

whom, and where, is necessary to assess GDPR compliance. Large-scale processing of special categories of personal data is held to particularly high compliance standards, and non-compliance is heavily sanctioned.¹⁴ The main focus of this book chapter will therefore be on processing of special categories of personal data for scientific research purposes, and in particular for open science purposes to help ascertain when data can be open, and when it must be closed. Finally, solutions that may help achieve the open science aim are presented.

The book chapter applies legal dogmatic methodology, which is the most common methodology in the legal field for assessing a legal question using relevant legal sources.

¹⁴ European Data Protection Board. Guidelines 04/2022 on the calculation of administrative fines under the GDPR. Version 2.0. Adopted on 24 May 2023.

2. Data identifiability

To assess whether the data can be open, or needs to be closed, one must first understand how the data one processes is classified legally. Processing is defined in Article 4(2) of the GDPR as “any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction”. Thus, processing is an umbrella term.

“Personal data” is defined in Article 4(1) of the GDPR as “any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’)”. It is further specified that an identifiable natural person is “one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person”. Recital 26 of the GDPR clarifies that pseudonymized data “which could be attributed to a natural person by the use of additional information should be considered to be information on an identifiable natural person”. In contrast, anonymous or anonymized data, is not considered personal data, and falls outside the scope of the GDPR. Hence, it is stated in Recital 26 that “The principles of data protection should therefore not apply to anonymous information, namely information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable. This Regulation does not therefore concern the processing of such anonymous information, including for statistical or research purposes.”

Anonymous data can from the point of view of data protection law be made openly available. However, other legislation may apply and must be considered, such as human rights, including antidiscrimination legislation. The potential for group discrimination should also be considered. Several research data repositories are built to facilitate processing of anonymous data, and anonymous data can be deposited in such repositories and shared openly worldwide. An example of such a repository is the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), which is a data repository under the European Elixir data infrastructure umbrella, based in the United Kingdom. Typically, such repositories require a confirmation that the data is anonymous, and so does ENA. This makes it important to understand the identifiability of the data one processes, and whether the processing is within or outside the scope of the GDPR. Of particular note is the fact that the definition of anonymous data varies between jurisdictions. For instance, the GDPR sets a higher threshold for considering data anonymous/anonymized than for instance the US Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA). This may be confusing to European readers of US scientific articles or journals, as these words are often used without being defined, and it may lead to a misconception that the terms have the same meaning on both sides of the Atlantic.

Recital 26 of the GDPR provides further clarification in this regard: “To determine whether a natural person is identifiable, account should be taken of all the means reasonably likely to be used, such as singling out, either by the controller or by another person to identify the natural person directly or indirectly.” Recital 26 continues: “To ascertain whether means are reasonably likely to be used to identify the natural person, account should be taken of all objective factors, such as the costs of and the amount of time required for identification, taking into consideration the available technology at the time of the processing and technological developments.” This indicates that it is a

dynamic test, where you not only need to assess the potential for reidentification today, but also toward the end of the processing time.¹⁵ If you intend to process the data for 20 years, you must therefore also consider the likely technological advances and cost reductions, and whether this may make it possible to identify an individual in the dataset 19 years from now. Some data is uniquely identifiable, such as a whole genome sequence, and can never be anonymous. Other data may be identifiable through linkage with other datasets or through the combination of variables within the research dataset.¹⁶ This risk is particularly high if the dataset includes demographic variables.¹⁷ If there is uncertainty regarding the data identifiability and the research is EU funded, the European Commission states that one should err on the side of caution and treat the data as personal data.¹⁸

Jurisprudence from the Court of Justice of the European Union adds further guidance on the distinction between anonymous and personal data. In *Patrick Breyer v Bundesrepublik Deutschland*, the court found dynamic IP addresses in the hands of an online media

¹⁵ Article 29 Data Protection Working Party. Opinion 4/2007 on the concept of personal data. WP 136. P. 15.

¹⁶ Na L, Yang C, Lo C, Zhao F, Fukuoka Y, Aswani A. Feasibility of Reidentifying Individuals in Large National Physical Activity Data Sets From Which Protected Health Information Has Been Removed With Use of Machine Learning. *JAMA Netw Open*. 2018;1(8):e186040. doi:10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2018.6040

¹⁷ Rocher, L., Hendrickx, J.M. & de Montjoye, YA. Estimating the success of re-identifications in incomplete datasets using generative models. *Nat Commun* **10**, 3069 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-10933-3>

¹⁸ European Commission. Ethics and data protection. 14 November 2018. P. 8. Available at

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/ethics/h2020_hi_ethics-data-protection_en.pdf [accessed 11 June 2023]

service provider to constitute personal data.¹⁹ The online media service provider was not able to identify individuals. It would only be possible to identify individuals if a cyberattack was committed, in which case a competent authority would be allowed to obtain and link the dynamic IP addresses from the online media service provider with data from the internet provider to identify the relevant individual for criminal proceedings. Likewise, in *Nowak*, both examination answers and comments made by an examiner were found to constitute personal data, and it was not required that all the information enabling the identification of the individual was in the hands of one person for the data to be considered personal data.²⁰ A recent judgment from the General Court, *SRB v EDPS*, marks a departure from the reasoning of the Court of Justice, and considers key-coded / pseudonymized comments to be anonymous in the hands of the recipient, and thus not personal data.²¹ It is currently unclear if the European Data Protection Supervisor will appeal this judgment to the Court of Justice, but for the sake of legal clarity, that would indeed be helpful.

A particular challenge relates to data that was previously considered anonymous and deposited in research repositories, but due to advances in the reidentification literature, is now considered personal data. For instance, a recent paper shows the possibility of

¹⁹ Court of Justice of the European Union. Case C-582/14 *Patrick Breyer v Bundesrepublik Deutschland*. 19 October 2016.

²⁰ Court of Justice of the European Union. Case C-434/16 *Nowak*. 20 December 2017.

²¹ General Court. Case T-557/20 *SRB v EDPS*. 26 April 2023.

reidentifying individuals from immune repertoire data / T-cell receptor genes.²² This is data that has been considered anonymous in the research community and has been shared openly, but a question now arises as to whether such data can still be considered anonymous or if it already is personal data subject to the provisions of the GDPR, or may become so in the near future. As mentioned above, to ascertain identifiability, all the means reasonably likely to be used to identify an individual should be considered. Currently, the described reidentification from T-cell receptor genes may involve means not reasonably likely to be used, but this may change with time as more data becomes available which may ease the reidentification. Another example is a Norwegian study where a regional ethics committee in 2011 considered whole genome sequence data in “genuinely anonymous”, a presumption that no longer holds today.²³ Hence, a release-and-forget strategy for data once considered anonymous is not feasible.²⁴ Identifiability must be continuously reassessed. If faced with a situation in which data previously considered anonymous is now considered personal data, one must bring the processing in line with data protection legislation, which can be a daunting task at that stage.

²² Dupic T, Bensouda Koraichi M, Minervina AA, Pogorelyy MV, Mora T, et al. (2021) Immune fingerprinting through repertoire similarity. PLOS Genetics 17(1): e1009301. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgen.1009301>

²³ Mascalzoni D, Bentzen HB, Ljøsne IB, et al. Are requirements to deposit data in research repositories compatible with the European Union’s general data protection regulation? Ann Int Med. 2019;170(5):332–334.

²⁴ Article 29 Data Protection Working Party. Opinion 05/2014 on Anonymisation Techniques. Adopted on 10 April 2014. WP 216. P. 24.

Often, metadata is provided openly to make data findable. However, also the identifiability of the metadata must be assessed. If the metadata is variable rich and specific, individuals may be identifiable based on the metadata alone. For instance, if the metadata contains the age of the research participants, the risk of reidentification increases the more specific the age is defined, such as date versus year versus year range. Similarly, inclusion in the metadata of rare diseases, intersex, twins, and other variables that relate to few individuals, increases the risk of re-identification.

3. Data transfer

Research data repositories can serve as useful archives, but also enable eased data discovery and access, and facilitate advanced analysis of data from several sources. Lists of recommended data repositories are often provided by scientific journals, and many data repositories are located outside the EU, entailing data transfer. For instance, in the genetics field, an often-recommended repository is the database of Genotypes and Phenotypes (dbGaP), a United States-based repository, set up under the United States National Institutes of Health.

The GDPR facilitates free movement of personal data within the European Economic Area (EEA). When personal data is to be transferred to countries outside the EEA, or to international organizations, there are rules in Chapter V of the GDPR in place to ensure that the EEA level of protection travels with the data.²⁵ Provision of remote data access

²⁵ Bentzen HB. *Exchange of human data across international boundaries*. Annual Review of Biomedical Data Science (2022), doi: [10.1146/annurev-biodatasci-122220-110811](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-biodatasci-122220-110811)

is also considered data transfer.²⁶ The European Commission has decided that some countries offer an adequate level of protection, and to these, data can be shared in the same manner as within the EEA. This includes Andorra, Argentina, Faroe Islands, Guernsey, Israel, Isle of Man, Japan, Jersey, New Zealand, Republic of Korea, Switzerland, the United Kingdom, Uruguay, and commercial organizations in Canada.²⁷

If an adequacy decision from the European Commission is not in place, and unless one of the Article 49 derogations for specific situations apply, an Article 46 appropriate safeguard must be provided and enforceable data subject rights and effective legal remedies for data subjects must be available.²⁸ Before setting up one of the eight appropriate safeguard available in the GDPR, a thorough Transfer Impact Assessment must be conducted to assess the level of protection in the importing country, and ensure the effectiveness of the appropriate safeguard, keeping in mind that supplementary measures of a legal, organizational, or technical nature may be necessary to achieve a

²⁶ European Data Protection Board. Guidelines 05/2021 on the Interplay between the application of Article 3 and the provisions on international transfers as per Chapter V of the GDPR. Version 2.0. Adopted on 14 February 2023.

²⁷ European Commission. Adequacy decisions. Available at https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection/international-dimension-data-protection/adequacy-decisions_en [Accessed 11 June 2023]

²⁸ Bentzen HB, Olav HK, Ursin G. Maximizing the GDPR potential for data transfers: first in Europe. *Lancet Reg Health Eur.* 2023 Mar 6;27:100600. doi: 10.1016/j.lanepe.2023.100600

sufficient level of protection.²⁹ This can be very time- and resource-consuming for research repositories that want to transfer data worldwide, and it may not be legally possible to transfer personal data to all entities.^{30,31} All three umbrella organizations representing the scientific academies of Europe, have expressed concern for the consequences this has to scientific advances.³² This means that personal data cannot be shared as widely across the world as anonymous data. Legally, data transfers are also complex to conduct, leading to a lack of harmonization in how the rules are applied across institutions. In addition to a legal data transfer mechanism, one must also ensure a lawful basis for the transfer, and other necessary contracts such as Controller to Controller Agreements, Joint Controller Agreements, or Data Processing Agreements must also be in place.

The *Schrems II* judgment from the Court of Justice of the European Union, and subsequent guidance from the European Data Protection Board, have showcased the

²⁹ European Data Protection Board. Recommendations 01/2020 on measures that supplement transfer tools to ensure compliance with the EU level of protection of personal data. Version 2.0 Adopted on 18 June 2021.

³⁰ Bentzen HB, Castro R, Fears R, et al. Remove obstacles to sharing health data with researchers outside of the European Union. *Nat Med.* 2021;27(8):1329–1333.

³¹ Ursin G, Stenbeck M, Chang-Claude J, et al. Data must be shared-also with researchers outside of Europe. *Lancet.* 2019;394(10212):1902–1903

³² Griffin G, ter Meulen V, Albert A et al. (2021). *International Sharing of Personal Health Data for Research. The ALLEA, EASAC and FEAM joint initiative on resolving the barriers of transferring public sector data outside the EU/EEA.* ALLEA, EASAC and FEAM (2021), doi: www.doi.org/10.26356/IHDT

difficulty of using US cloud providers for personal data processing, as US intelligence authorities have access to the data processed by these companies.³³ This challenge extends to the use of US cloud providers' servers located in the EEA, and may pose a problem for data repositories relying on one of these much-used cloud providers such as Amazon Web Services, Google Cloud, and Microsoft Azure. The European Commission has launched the adoption procedure for a draft adequacy decision, which if adopted, will re-enable the use of certified US cloud providers.³⁴ However, the draft has been met with severe criticism, including from the European Parliament, which has adopted a Resolution calling for the draft adequacy decision not to be adopted before meaningful reforms are implemented in the United States.³⁵ Legal action against the adequacy decision, if adopted, is likely.³⁶

A personal data transfer to dbGaP can exemplify a further issue. As mentioned, this repository is, as many repositories in the medical field in the United States, set up under the US National Institutes of Health (NIH). NIH is a federal institution, protected by sovereign immunity. This means that it is not possible to fulfil the Article 46 condition for establishment of an appropriate safeguard, that "enforceable data subject rights and

³³ Court of Justice of the European Union. Case C-311/18 *Data Protection Commissioner v Facebook Ireland Limited and Maximilian Schrems*. 16 July 2020.

³⁴ European Commission. EU-US data transfers. Available at https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection/international-dimension-data-protection/eu-us-data-transfers_en [accessed 11 June 2023]

³⁵ European Parliament. European Parliament resolution of 11 May 2023 on the adequacy of the protection afforded by the EU-US Data Privacy Framework (2023/2501(RSP))

³⁶ Noyb. Statement on US adequacy decision by the European Commission. 13 December 2022. Available at <https://noyb.eu/en/statement-eu-comission-adequacy-decision-us> [Accessed 11 June 2023]

effective legal remedies for data subjects are available". Personal data transfers to US federal institutions have therefore been halted.³⁷ This also affects data transfers to research data repositories, such as dbGaP.

In Europe, several of the main repositories in the medical field are under EMBL-EBI in Europe. EMBL-EBI is formally set up as an international organization. This means that a Chapter V data transfer mechanism must be in place for personal data transfer to such repositories for the transfers to be legal. The same applies to other international organizations, such as the United Nations, hereunder-personal data transfers to the World Health Organization.

When personal data is transferred from a non-EEA country to the EEA or to another non-EEA country, the rules of the exporting non-EEA country applies.

When choosing to transfer data to a repository, one should also be mindful that one may become subject to the laws and courts of several jurisdictions simultaneously, and the laws of these countries may not be harmonized and may directly contradict.³⁸

³⁷ Eiss R. Confusion over Europe's data-protection law is stalling scientific progress. *Nature*. 2020 Aug;584(7822):498. doi: 10.1038/d41586-020-02454-7.

³⁸ Bentzen HB, Svantesson DJB. Jurisdictional challenges related to DNA processing in transnational clouds. In: Svantesson DJB, Kloza D, eds. *Transatlantic Data Privacy Relationships as a Challenge for Democracy*. European Integration and Democracy Series, vol. 4. Cambridge, United Kingdom: Intersentia; 2017:241-60

4. Informed consent compliance

The original researchers are the ones who have ensured that informed consent to research participation has been obtained from the participants. Informed consent is a research ethics instrument, with roots back to the Nuremberg Code, and later included *inter alia* in the Declaration of Helsinki and many domestic research ethics laws.^{39,40} When data is transferred to a repository, the transfer and further use by other researchers must be within the limits of the original consent. This places responsibility on the researchers to ensure that these limits are respected. For some research, not only compliance with individual informed consent is necessary, but also compliance with collective consent, as is the case for instance with research on the indigenous Sami population.⁴¹

Some repositories, including the aforementioned dbGaP, have solved this by mandating a copy of the information sheet and consent form template to be uploaded. Another repository that has chosen to do the same is the European Genome-Phenome Archive (EGA).

³⁹ Nuremberg Code, Washington, DC, US Government Printing Office, 1949, pp 181-182.

⁴⁰ World Medical Association. WMA Declaration of Helsinki – Ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects. Adopted June 1964, last amended October 2013.

⁴¹ The Sami Parliament. Sakkyndig etisk komité for samisk helseforskning. Available at <https://sametinget.no/barnevern-helse-og-sosial/etiske-retningslinjer-for-samisk-helseforskning-og-kollektiv-samtykke/sakkyndig-etisk-komite-for-samisk-helseforskning/> [Accessed 11 June 2023]

Even when uploading a blank informed consent template, one should consider who will assess the document. Some repositories rely on Data Access Committees that do not include any of the original researchers, and may be located in a different country under another cultural context, and the document may be translated.⁴² This involves a risk of misinterpretation.

5. Lawful basis for further data processing

One must distinguish between informed consent to research participation and a lawful basis for data processing according to Articles 6 and 9 of the GDPR, which can, but does not need to be consent.

In line with the principle of lawfulness, fairness and transparency, personal data shall in accordance with Article 5(1) be processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject. In cases where the data processing *is* based on consent, the consent must in accordance with Article 4(11) of the GDPR be a “freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her”. The information that should be provided to the data subject is listed in Articles 13 and 14 of the GDPR, including the identity of the controller and the purposes of the processing, and the information should according to

⁴² Mascalzoni D, Bentzen HB, Ljøsne IB, et al. Are requirements to deposit data in research repositories compatible with the European Union's general data protection regulation? *Ann Int Med.* 2019;170(5):332–334.

Article 12(1) be provided in a “concise, transparent, intelligible and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language”. Recital 32 clarifies that silence or inactivity do not constitute consent. The controller should be able to demonstrate that the data subject has consented, see Article 7(1) and Recital 42. The data subject has the right to withdraw the consent at any time, and it should be as easy to withdraw as to give consent, see Article 7(3). This requires effective consent withdrawal procedures in place, also when data is deposited in repositories or further used by other researchers. The European Data Protection Board had signaled that it will provide further clarification on the requirement of a lawful basis for further processing for scientific research purposes by the original or a subsequent controller.⁴³

It is acknowledged in Recital 33 that it may not always be feasible to fully identify the purpose of personal data processing for scientific research purposes at the time of data collection. In such cases, data subjects are allowed to consent to “certain areas of scientific research when in keeping with recognised ethical standards for scientific research”. The European Data Protection Board has specified that this does not disapply the obligation to obtain specific consent. In cases where a purpose cannot be fully specified, one must therefore seek other ways to respect the essence of the consent requirement, for instance by first ensuring a general consent, and subsequently obtaining specified consent for each project.⁴⁴

⁴³ European Data Protection Board. EDPB Document on response to the request from the European Commission for clarifications on the consistent application of the GDPR, focusing on health research. Adopted on 2 February 2021. P. 6.

⁴⁴ European Data Protection Board. Guidelines 05/2020 on consent under Regulation 2016/679. Version 1.1. Adopted on 4 May 2020. Pp. 30-31.

6. Technical and organizational measures

The principle of accountability entails that the controller is responsible for, and should be able to demonstrate compliance with, the six data protection principles listed in Article 5(1). Amongst these is the principle of integrity and confidentiality, see Article 5(1)(f). The controller is under Article 24 required to implement appropriate technical and organizational measures to ensure and to be able to demonstrate that processing is performed in accordance with the GDPR.

Recital 49 elaborates that information security is “the ability of a network or an information system to resist, at a given level of confidence, accidental events or unlawful or malicious actions that compromise the availability, authenticity, integrity and confidentiality of stored or transmitted personal data, and the security of the related services offered by, or accessible via, those networks and systems”. The principle of integrity and confidentiality entails appropriate security using appropriate technical and organizational measures, to protect against unauthorized or unlawful data processing, and against accidental loss, destruction or damage. The level of security should be appropriate to the risk, see Article 32.

The challenge related to open science, is that once data has been deposited in a repository or shared with other researchers, the original research institution may lose control of the technical and organizational measures.

It should be noted that even when the research data does not include personal data, technical and organizational measures to ensure information security remain important

to protect other interests, for instance intellectual property rights related to algorithms or analysis methods.⁴⁵

7. Data minimization, purpose limitation, and storage limitation

The principle of data minimization in Article 5(1)(c) entails that personal data shall be adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed. For scientific research, Article 89(1) requires technical and organizational measures to be in place, particularly to ensure respect for the principle of data minimization. This can include pseudonymization. If the scientific research purposes can be achieved with anonymized data, or it is only necessary for the data to be identifiable in the beginning of the project, the data should be anonymized as soon as identification is no longer needed.

The aim of the principle of data minimization is to avoid a surveillance society, where data is kept in case it may come in useful at some point. The principle therefore does not support long-term, unspecified data retention.⁴⁶ It can also be questioned which procedures repositories have in place to ensure respect for this principle. The core aim of the principle of data minimization may be at odds with the aim of open science,

⁴⁵ See below under point 13. Blockchain may contribute to ensure authenticity, confidentiality, and integrity of data.

⁴⁶ Mascalzoni D, Bentzen HB, Ljøsne IB, et al. Are requirements to deposit data in research repositories compatible with the European Union's general data protection regulation? *Ann Int Med.* 2019;170(5):332–334.

hereunder with the provision of open data. As such, it raises questions related to the compliance of funders and scientific journals' open science policies with data protection law.

The principle of data minimization is closely related to the principle of storage limitation in Article 5(1)(e). Storage limitation entails that personal data shall be kept in a form that permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed. But personal data may be stored for longer periods insofar as it will be processed solely for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, an example of one of the derogations in the GDPR establishing more lenient rules when the data processing is for scientific research purposes.

Another closely related principle is that of purpose limitation in Article 5(1)(b). It provides that personal data shall be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes.⁴⁷ However, as mentioned above, further processing for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes is not considered incompatible with the initial purposes. However, the new purpose must still be specified.

⁴⁷ Bentzen HB. *Context as key: The protection of personal integrity by means of the purpose limitation principle*. In: Kosta E, Leenes R, Kamara I (eds.) *Research Handbook on EU Data Protection Law*. Edward Elgar (2022)

8. Data subject rights

Individuals have a fundamental right to data protection pursuant to Article 8 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union. Several data subject rights are enshrined in the GDPR, though not all always apply if the data processing is for scientific research purposes. It may be challenging to ensure effective data subject rights in repositories.

Data subjects have the right of access, see Article 15, which *inter alia* includes right to information about the recipients or categories of recipient to whom the personal data have been or will be disclosed. It was recently clarified by the Court of Justice of the European Union in the *Österreichische Post* judgment that the data subject can choose whether they wish to know the recipients individually or only by category.⁴⁸

Data subjects also have a right to rectification of inaccurate or incomplete personal data, see Article 16, and a right to erasure according to Article 17. Data subjects also have the right to restriction of processing according to Article 18, and the right to object to processing of personal data, see Article 21.

However, when personal data is processed for scientific research purposes, Article 89(2) stipulates that EU or Member State law may provide for derogations from the right of access, the right to rectification, the right to restriction of processing, and the right to

⁴⁸ Court of Justice of the European Union. Case C-154/21 *RW v Österreichische Post AG*. 12 January 2023.

object in so far as such rights are likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the specific purposes, and such derogations are necessary for the fulfilment of those purposes. If so, there must be compliance with the conditions and safeguards in Article 89(1), hereunder data minimization. A similar exception is in place for the right to erasure, but for that right the exception is provided in the GDPR itself, see Article 17(2)(d).

9. Federated data sharing and controlled access

A controller is defined in Article 4(7) as “the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data”. A processor is defined in Article 4(8) as “a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller”. Understanding which role each entity has is crucial in determining legal responsibilities under the GDPR.

To ensure data protection law compliance whilst enabling open science, repositories providing controlled data access and federated data sharing, are set up. One such example is the European Genome-Phenome Archive (EGA), a federated EEA-based repository under the European Elixir umbrella. In the case of EGA, the repository is a processor that stores the data and makes the metadata the controller provides publicly available. The original research institution is the controller. A Data Processing Agreement is in place between the controller and the processor. The Data Access Committee is under the auspices of the original research institution, the controller. The ethics approval and the information sheet and consent form template must be provided to the repository alongside a clarification of the lawful basis for data processing, and all

processing in the repository is limited to the conditions of the approvals. Whenever someone requests data access, all agreements are made directly between the original research institution and the new research institution. This may involve a Transfer Impact Assessment and establishment of a Chapter V of the GDPR legal data transfer mechanism if the new research institution is outside the EEA. It may also entail a Data Protection Impact Assessment, and typically a Controller-to-Controller agreement. This arrangement respects the FAIR principles and is GDPR compliant, but is cumbersome and time- and resource-demanding if one wants access to numerous datasets from different institutions. Please note that this description of EGA does not apply to all repositories, as they are all set up differently. Note in particular that not all repositories will be considered processors as the threshold for being considered a controller or joint controller is very low.⁴⁹

There may be a need to link several repositories, and each repository may have different role and access procedures. For instance, for Covid-19 research, it could be useful to link data from EGA with ENA, and it may also be useful with linkage with data from repositories outside the EEA, such as dbGaP. This is currently very difficult and time-consuming. Large EU projects are working on solving such data linkage challenges.⁵⁰

⁴⁹ European Data Protection Board. Guidelines 07/2020 on the concepts of controller and processor in the GDPR. Version 2.1. Adopted on 07 July 2021.

⁵⁰ For instance the EU funded BeYond-COVID (BY-COVID) project available at <https://by-covid.org> [Accessed 11 June] and the European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) project available at <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu> [Accessed 11 June 2023]

Some federated sharing tools and environments are already set up, such as DataSHIELD, which is infrastructure and R packages that enables remote, non-disclosive analysis of sensitive research data.^{51,52} However, there is concern that the use of such tools may negatively impact the information security at each site as access is typically required behind the firewall. There is furthermore concern related to federated training that even when the algorithm is sent to the data, instead of the other way around, it may still be feasible to identify individuals in the resulting model. This is therefore not necessarily a solution if the aim is for the data processing to fall outside the scope of the GDPR. When setting up federated solutions involving several repositories, the established base must be considered, meaning the infrastructure and technical and organizational set up already in place. Nevertheless, federated sharing may allow substantially faster data access and linkage.

⁵¹ Budin-Ljøsne I, Burton P, Isaeva J, et al. DataSHIELD: an ethically robust solution to multiple-site individual-level data analysis. *Public Health Genomics*. 2015;18:87.

⁵² DataSHIELD Secure Bioscience Collaboration. Available at <https://www.datashield.org> [Accessed 11 June 2023]

10. Data Protection Impact Assessment

If a processing is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals, the controller shall according to Article 35 carry out an assessment of the impact of the envisaged processing operations on the protection of personal data. This refers to risks in a wide sense, and includes for instance discrimination potential. The diversity of the dataset may be a relevant factor to consider in this regard. Such an assessment is an important accountability tool called a Data Protection Impact Assessment, and it lays out both the risks and the mitigating measures to address them. A Data Protection Impact Assessment is particularly required if there is processing on a large scale of special categories of personal data. When assessing if something is “large scale”, the Article 29 Data Protection Working Party recommended considering the following factors: the number of data subjects concerned, either as a specific number or as a proportion of the relevant population; the volume of data and/or the range of different data items being processed; the duration, or permanence, of the data processing activity; and the geographical extent of the processing activity.⁵³

The Article 29 Data Protection Working Party has provided guidelines, endorsed by the current European Data Protection Board, which serve as a useful reference on how to

⁵³ The Article 29 Data Protection Working Party. Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is “likely to result in a high risk” for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679. Adopted on 4 April 2017. As last Revised and Adopted on 4 October 2017. WP248.rev.01. P. 10.

conduct a Data Protection Impact Assessment and how to determine whether processing is likely to result in a high risk.⁵⁴

11. Incidental findings and reporting obligations

If research findings are made that are of relevance to a research participant's current or future health or quality of life, this information must be offered to them.⁵⁵ This follows from the Council of Europe Additional Protocol to the Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine, concerning Biomedical Research.⁵⁶ In communicating such information, an individual's wish not to know must also be respected. Only 12 Council of Europe countries have ratified the Additional Protocol to date.

It is unclear how such legal reporting obligations are fulfilled when new researchers reuse research data.

⁵⁴ The Article 29 Data Protection Working Party. Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is "likely to result in a high risk" for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679. Adopted on 4 April 2017. As last Revised and Adopted on 4 October 2017. WP248.rev.01.

⁵⁵ Vears DF, Hallowell N, Bentzen HB, et al. *A practical checklist for return of results from genomic research in the European context*. European Journal of Human Genetics (2023), doi: 10.1038/s41431-023-01328-6

⁵⁶ Council of Europe. Additional Protocol to the Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine, concerning Biomedical Research. Council of Europe Treaty Series - No. 195.

In EU funded projects, establishment of an incidental findings policy is part of the ethics self-assessment.⁵⁷ This is typically quite broadly understood, to also include for instance findings about criminal offences such as uncovering of domestic violence in the course of a research project, and also a wide range of findings in the medical field, not only from genetic research, but also for instance imaging such as MRI.

⁵⁷ European Commission. EU Grants. How to complete your ethics self-assessment. Version 2.0 13 July 2021.

12. Private companies

Typically, the data deposited in research repositories stem from public research institutions. Private companies are not always as eager to share data they have collected or generated openly.

When private companies are the new user of personal data from public research institutions, empirical research shows that benefit sharing measures should be considered to retain societal acceptance.^{58,59} This can include either benefits to the individuals that have contributed data about them, benefits to society, or both.

A repository should be governed by an intellectual property management plan, considering both the infrastructure and the content, and explaining for instance if the database will be protected by copyright, sui generis European database rights, or open source. Some repositories are commercialized and demand access fees.

13. *De lege ferenda* and the technological state of art

Blockchains are “distributed digital ledgers of cryptographically signed transactions that are grouped into blocks. Each block is cryptographically linked to the previous one

⁵⁸ Shah N, Johansson JV, Haraldsdóttir E et al. *Governing health data across changing contexts: A focus group study of citizen's views in England, Iceland, and Sweden*. International Journal of Medical Informatics (2021), doi: 10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2021.104623

⁵⁹ Johansson JV, Bentzen HB, Shah N et al. *Publics' preferences for sharing health data: a discrete choice experiment*. JMIR Medical Informatics (2021), doi: 2021/7/e2961

(making it tamper evident) after validation and undergoing a consensus decision. As new blocks are added, older blocks become more difficult to modify (creating tamper resistance). New blocks are replicated across copies of the ledger within the network, and any conflicts are resolved automatically using established rules".^{60,61}

Blockchain offers immutable traceability, which is an advantage in open science, as it not only can prevent falsification and misuse, but also provide a good overview of data users. It may serve as a tool to meet ethical and legal requirement, such as the FAIR principles and information security.⁶² Personal data is typically not stored on the blockchain, but metadata and keys/hash values used to secure and control access to personal data stored off-line can be.^{63,64}

When processing personal data, and in particular special categories of personal data, the open data aspect of open science should be achieved by controlled access. In general, EEA based repositories create significantly fewer legal challenges than non-EEA

⁶⁰ Jansen AJ & ØInes S. ROSiE D6.3: Comparison of existing blockchain technologies to safeguard responsible OS. 31 August 2022.

⁶¹ The National Institute of Standards and Technology. NISTIR 8202: Blockchain Technology Overview (2018).

⁶² Jansen AJ & ØInes S. ROSiE D6.3: Comparison of existing blockchain technologies to safeguard responsible OS. 31 August 2022.

⁶³ DIN SPEC 4997: Privacy by Blockchain design: A standardised model for processing personal data using blockchain technology.

⁶⁴ Jansen AJ & ØInes S. ROSiE D6.3: Comparison of existing blockchain technologies to safeguard responsible OS. 31 August 2022.

based repositories. However, also within the EEA, there are legal challenges caused by differing legal interpretations and domestic rules introduced in addition to those of the GDPR pertaining to the use of health data for secondary purposes.⁶⁵ Domestic rules hindering secondary use should be harmonized with the GDPR. Still, even with harmonized EEA rules, achieving open science is not simply a matter of uploading data to a repository. One needs to consider every step in the deposit and access data flow, including all legal documentation required for each step and the time it takes to produce that documentation, and whose role it is to ensure what. Without proper planning, legal bottlenecks may form, particularly when data is requested from outside the EEA. New technological advances that may contribute to privacy and ethics by design should be considered.

⁶⁵ Towards European Health Data Space. Deliverable 5.2. Recommendations for European countries when planning national legislation on secondary use of health data. 1 March 2023. Available at <https://tehdas.eu/results/tehdas-study-member-states-to-harmonise-national-legislation-to-enable-the-secondary-use-of-health-data/> [Accessed 11 June 2023]

